

THE MAIN FEATURES OF THE EXPEDIENCY OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ENGLISH SPEAKING SCIENCE STUDENTS CLUB (ES³C)***Poliukhovych A.,****4th year student,**specialty 014 Secondary education (Physics)****Rokytska H.****PhD in Physics and Mathematics,**Experimental and Theoretical Physics and Astronomy Department,**Ukrainian State Dragomanov University**Kyiv, Ukraine***Abstract**

The expediency of implementation an English-speaking scientific student conversation club in the fields of physics and mathematics is under consideration. Considering the growing demand for improving knowledge of a foreign language, the speaking science club allows students of physical and mathematical specialties and those who want to improve their language skills to unite to discuss not only topics of common interest, but also scientific topics that are in educational specializations. Therefore, improving student's spoken English and communication skills, getting to know wonderful people, as well as improving and acquiring the latest scientific knowledge in the physico-mathematical direction and expanding one's scientific outlook are very relevant in our time.

Keywords: Education, speaking club, science club, english-speaking student club, science, english-speaking science club, physical and mathematical direction.

In today's society, science student groups for informal communication are an excellent opportunity to exchange ideas with other students who share similar views, values and interests in science.

During meetings, students train in understanding and analyzing opposing points of view, learn to express their disagreement or admiration, and quickly respond to counterarguments. These skills are extremely important for life abroad and in situations related to the chosen specialization. In addition, they are useful for preparing for international exams and writing essays or other academic and research papers.

Physics and mathematics speaking clubs can exist at various levels, including universities, scientific institutions, and public organizations. They facilitate the exchange of knowledge, discussions, and joint research on topics of interest to participants. Such clubs can organize lectures, seminars, debating tournaments and other events for in-depth study of science, language and support of the scientific community.

A huge number of textbooks and other resources are available on the modern Internet for self-study of the English language and deepening of knowledge in the field of the latest scientific research. However, achieving a high level of speaking skill becomes difficult without real practice.[1] Therefore, with the help of speaking clubs, you can achieve the desired results of language proficiency and, in turn, expand your knowledge in the relevant field of science studied by students of each faculty involved.

The Speaking Science Club is a community of students and interested individuals who come together to discuss scientific topics, improve English and develop communication skills. The goal is to deepen knowledge, expand worldviews, and exchange ideas through lectures, seminars, and other scientific events. [2]

Language is one of the most important bricks in the foundation of every nation. It is in it that the deepest

sources of the people's consciousness and mentality are reflected and recorded, and folk wisdom and ancient knowledge are encoded. It represents the people in the world, is the halo of the nation and the ethnic border. In combination with the latest scientific research achievements, it is very useful, in combination with language practice, to improve the entire scientific and worldview potential. [3]

Speaking club provides an excellent opportunity for regular speaking practice, which significantly contributes to improving speaking and listening comprehension skills, as well as reducing your accent (if you set such a goal for yourself).

Fortunately, going to chat groups is now available to almost everyone. If you cannot afford clubs with tutors in language schools, look for free meetings on the initiative of those who want to communicate in English - they can be found in many cities of Ukraine. If there are no such events near you, you can find them online or even organize them yourself. The main disadvantage of such informal clubs is that you may lack an experienced teacher to give you feedback on your speaking. [6]

This is the most accessible analogue of immersion in a language environment where you will not have the opportunity to switch to your native language, thanks to which you will quickly train your brain to think in English and, accordingly, speak in this language.

If you are lucky enough to attend conversation clubs with native speakers, then you will have a unique opportunity to learn the living language of the Neites, which is often not found in textbooks: slang, idioms, dialect expressions, etc. In addition, regular interaction with a real British and American accent will be very helpful.

In addition, you will be able to make useful acquaintances and learn more about the life and culture of other countries, which will never be superfluous. It is

also useful to learn about studies in other countries and at what level they consider popular science content.

In speaking clubs, no one expects everyone to communicate in perfect English. By listening to other participants, you will see that no one speaks perfectly. You will see that mistakes and "stucks" are part of any communication process. In the process of communication, you get confirmation that you are understood, and you learn to understand others, exactly as it happens when communicating in your native language. Rejection of perfectionism is an important mental factor, overcoming which increases motivation and satisfaction with the process.

Classes at the English Speaking Science Students Club have their own distinctive features. The goal is not to learn new things, but to practice your communication skills. Here, students practice and consolidate already existing knowledge. Visiting the club will help increase the speed of spoken language and the formulation of one's thoughts using the topics of the latest scientific research. The meeting takes place in a group format. Usually, the number of students at one meeting of the club is limited, too many people will prevent everyone from expressing their opinion, but the total number of students in the club can be arbitrary, only organized according to certain interests and consideration of scientific research news. [7]

Topics for Speaking Club are usually chosen in advance. They should be interesting enough for all members of the community. It is possible to discuss, for example, why our universe is the way it is, how this universe arose, how it is developing and what will happen to it in the future? [5] All these questions have always interested people in one form or another. There remain many mysteries and strange phenomena that we still do not understand well. If the topic is interesting, the number of active participants will be much higher. In addition to discussions, there are other interesting formats of classes. [1]

And if students in English Speaking Science Students Club write down their answers to questions, or prepare questions in advance for the topic discussed at the next meeting of the club, then the results will be even better. The club members have time during the interval between meetings to familiarize themselves with the main terms for the proposed discussion, namely, to find the necessary phrases in the dictionary to express their opinion, and, perhaps, to prepare a debate on the considered topic of the physical and mathematical direction. As a result, answers and discussions will be clearer, and students will increase and activate their vocabulary.

In the speaking club, the English language is not practiced to the point of automatism. Instead, what students are already good at in the process of real communication is actively used, namely, consideration of current research in science and technology. As during seminar classes, during the discussion of a popular science topic, no one will correct students' mistakes, criticize, or give grades.

Since this format is as close as possible to a real communication situation, the result of the meetings is

satisfaction from communication, a better understanding of one's own views and confidence that the club members understand.

Having participated in a conversation club of this kind for at least six months, students are convinced of how much their attitude to learning and using English, to the process of communication and discussion of popular science topics has changed.

The choice of format depends on the imagination of the organizer, and there are many possibilities. Interesting scenarios make classes even more exciting, especially useful when discussions take place with native speakers. This allows you to assess how clear your language is and helps you learn to understand English by ear. Groups in the club are usually formed according to the level of participants, which makes the classes interesting. Otherwise, some will talk a lot, while others may feel uncomfortable and uneasy.

The club will be useful for those who like to communicate and want to keep up with the latest scientific research. English Science Students Speaking Club is a meeting place for like-minded people, people who have a common goal. Here you can find new friends, support. [4] This format of communication provides not only the practice of language constructions, but also develops communication skills, and also provides an opportunity to expand one's horizons and develop new connections during the consideration of certain topics, causing the interlocutors numerous questions. To participate in classes, it is necessary to have a sufficient supply of language vocabulary, grammar and a scientific level of understanding of the main basic phenomena and processes of science. This is necessary to be able to express complex ideas.

Conclusions. The English Speaking Science Students Club was created so that students of our faculty could freely discuss various scientific topics of physics and mathematics not only in their native Ukrainian, but also in English. Here, students have the opportunity to spend time with benefit and develop as an individual.

Involvement of students of different faculties in the club has a number of important advantages. Interdisciplinarity: students from different faculties bring different approaches and knowledge, which contributes to a broader consideration of problems and tasks. It can promote innovation and creative thinking and popularize scientific content. Expanding horizons: because participants have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with various scientific fields that can be useful for their education and career. Generalization and dissemination of the best experience of scientific activity, which is related to the organization and implementation of activities on civil protection issues and daily activities of management bodies and civil protection forces and other issues related to obtaining new scientific and applied scientific results and their implementation in practical activity and educational process. Collaboration skills: Teamwork with students from different departments helps develop collaboration and communication skills that are useful in any professional field. Enrichment of experience: they can learn new research methods and approaches that can improve the quality

of their research. Therefore, the involvement of students of different faculties in scientific clubs contributes to deeper and more diverse learning and development.

References

1. <https://ngp-ua.info/2021/09/53256>
2. Rokytska H.V., Polyukhovych A.F. The expediency of implementation an English Speaking Science Students club (ES3C) // Proceedings of I International Scientific and Practical Conference "Current challenges of science and education" (18-20 September 2023, Berlin, Germany). – 2023. – P. 139-142.
3. <https://library.vn.ua/pro-biblioteku/klubi-gurtki/rozmovnij-klub-ukraiinske-slovo>
4. <https://kursymov.com.ua/tpost/eefa3vkj31-speaking-club-with-clark-hughes>
5. https://science.knu.ua/?id=138&bxajaxid=97b61c454cda57cd8f6d4f2e1a6e5428&PAGEN_1=74&SHOWALL_2=1
6. <https://www.education.ua/blog/48294/>
7. Rokytska H.V., Polyukhovych A.F. Implementation of the English Science Students Speaking club (ES3C) in the fields of physics and mathematics // Collection of theses of reports based on the materials of the international scientific and methodical conference "Technological support of STEM education in the conditions of training of a specialist in the field of science and mathematics" (26 - October 27, 2023, Kamianets-Podilskyi, Ukraine). - 2023. - P. 46-48.